

THE DEVELOPMENT OF SIGN LANGUAGE COMMUNICATION WITH THE EMOTIONAL FEELINGS IN DEAF CHILD

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Annotation. This article is devoted to the social situation in which a child with hearing impairment finds himself is of great importance in the emergence of his peculiarities in the development of emotions and the formation of certain personality traits. The development of the emotional sphere of deaf children is influenced by certain unfavorable factors. Violation of verbal communication partially isolates a deaf person from the speaking people around him, which creates difficulties in assimilating social experience.

The social situation in which a child with hearing impairment finds himself is of great importance in the emergence of his peculiarities in the development of emotions and the formation of certain personality traits.

Deaf children cannot perceive the expressive side of oral speech and music. A delay in speech development negatively affects the awareness of one's own and others' emotional states and causes simplification of interpersonal relationships. Later introduction to fiction impoverishes the world of emotional experiences of a deaf child and leads to difficulties in developing empathy for other people and characters in works of fiction.

The main directions in the development of the emotional sphere in a child with impaired hearing are the same as in a child with normal hearing: both are born with a ready-made mechanism for assessing the significance of external influences, phenomena and situations from the point of view of their relationship to life activity - with the emotional tone of sensations. Already in the first year of life, differences are felt between hearing children and children with hearing impairments in the development of emotions themselves, which often increase in the future.

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A number of studies by domestic and foreign authors examined the problems of the unique emotional development of deaf children, caused by the inferiority of emotional and verbal communication with people around them from the first days of their life, which causes difficulties in the socialization of children, their adaptation to society, and neurotic reactions (E. Levine, K. Meadow, N. G. Morozova, V. F. Matveev, V. Pietrzak and others).

Under normal conditions, children with hearing impairments have limited ability to perceive emotionally altered speech intonation. The lag and originality in the development of speech affect the mastery of words and phrases denoting certain emotional states. Gradually, they master natural facial-gestural structures for communicating with other people and sign language, adopted in communication between the deaf, so there is a lack of understanding of speech intonation and in the development of verbal speech are compensated by increased attention to the facial expressions and gestures of others, and the designation of emotional states by means of sign language.

Due to limited verbal and play communication, as well as the inability to listen and understand the reading of stories and fairy tales, young deaf children have difficulty understanding the desires, intentions, and experiences of their peers.

At the beginning of their stay in kindergarten, children do not come to the aid of their comrades and do not express sympathy for each other. The sympathetic attitude of deaf children towards each other is stimulated by an effective instruction - pity, stroke or an invitation (by imitation) to empathy, sympathy for the crying person. A positive emotional tone is created through the formation of role-playing games, holidays, birthdays, and the general way of life in kindergarten with an attitude towards another person, another child, his experiences and difficulties.

In recognizing emotions in all variants of images, deaf preschoolers are significantly inferior to their hearing peers. They are characterized by difficulties in understanding literary works, the causes and consequences of the actions of certain characters, in establishing the causes of emotional experiences, the nature of the emerging relationships between characters; empathy for certain literary characters arises late (and often remains rather one-dimensional).

Self-esteem and level of aspirations. Deaf children's self-image is often inaccurate; they are characterized by exaggerated ideas about their abilities and how others evaluate them. Deaf children with deaf parents have more adequate self-esteem compared to deaf children with hearing parents. Deaf primary schoolchildren with an average level of intellectual development generally have inflated self-esteem. Hearing-impaired primary schoolchildren with a high intellectual level generally have adequate self-esteem, that is, they generally correspond in terms of personality development to normally developing children of the same age. Deaf and hard of hearing children of primary school age most adequately assess their educational activities. To evaluate this activity, there are objective external indicators - a mark, the basis of which leads to a more adequate analysis of academic success. Hearing-impaired primary schoolchildren evaluate themselves more critically as a student and as a person compared to their deaf peers. By the way, it is important to say that self-esteem plays an important role in the formation of behavioral processes and determines the level of its aspirations. Self-esteem and aspirations are largely determined by a person's emotional well-being and the degree of maturity of his personality.

The formation of self-esteem and level of aspirations reflect those contradictions that can become factors in the mental development of an individual. The level of aspirations, on the one hand, depends on a person's abilities, which are subjective conditions for the successful performance of activities, and their adequate assessment; on the other hand, it determines the formation of these abilities. As a rule, the level of aspiration is characterized as a stable generalized personality trait. Its first manifestations are observed already in children two to three years old with normal development of their personality.

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